

Creator(s):

1. Dictionaries (stored as a concatenated dictionary from these two resources):

Cleasby-Vigfusson: Sean Crist main creator; Peter M. Broadwell and Timothy Tangherlini data clean-up and formatting

Zoega: Timothy Tangherlini and David Gabriel creator; Peter M. Broadwell and Timothy Tangherlini data clean-up and formatting

Concatenated dictionary: Peter Broadwell

File: dictionary_20140605.json

2. Saga texts:

Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda: Timothy Tangherlini main creator; Zoe Borovsky data clean-up and formatting

File: allvol.zip

Tagged saga texts (Output from IceMorph): Kryztof Urban, Timothy Tangherlini, Aurelijus Vijunas main creators

File: icemorph_corpus-2014-06-01.zip

3. Tagged corpora:

Expert corpus: Aurelijus Vijunas, Timothy Tangherlini, and Jackson Crawford main creators

Gold corpus: Aurelijus Vijunas and Kryztof Urban main creators

File: tagged_corpora_20140605.json

Title: IceMorph morphological analysis data files

Keywords: Old Icelandic, Morphosyntactic tagging, POS-tagging, Old Icelandic dictionaries, Old Icelandic training data

Abstract: This dataset consists of four main resources: a concatenated dictionary of Old Icelandic parsed for word class and inflectional detail; a corpus of Old Icelandic sagas in plain text and chunked by chapter; a tagged version of the same text, output of the IceMorph system; a training corpus labeled “Expert” for training and testing a machine

learning module; and a training corpus labeled “Gold” for training and testing a machine learning module.

Methods: Datasets (1) dictionary (2a) saga texts were generated using OCR. Dataset (2b) is the output of the IceMorph tagging system. Datasets (3a) and (3b) were generated by hand-tagging.

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